

REPORT #12

Evolution of educational equity and school segregation in Italy

Assessment and promotion of educational equity in secondary education: secondary analysis of PISA and training of key educational agents (Evaluación y promoción de la equidad Educativa en educación sEcundaria: Análisis secundario de las evaluaciones PISA y formación de agentes educativos clave)

Project PID2021-125775NB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ and FEDER A way to make Europe

Authors:

Fernando Martínez Abad

Adriana Gamazo García

Table of contents

EVIDENCE project: phase one	3
National project R+D 2021 (Spain) EVIDENCE.....	3
Phase one: evolution of educational equity	3
Interpretation of equity indicators	4
Indicators for equity as equal achievement.....	4
Indicators for equity as equal opportunities.....	5
Evolution of equity indicators in the country	6
Evolution of equity as equal achievement.....	6
Evolution of equity as equal opportunities.....	8
Global score of the indicators	11

EVIDENCE project: phase one

National project R+D 2021 (Spain) EVIDENCE

EVIDENCE is a research and development project (2021 project call, reference PID2021-125775NB-I00) granted by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and coordinated by the Educational Assessment and Guidance Research Group (GE2O), which is integrated in the Research Group of Interaction and E-Learning (GRIAL) of the University Institute for Educational Sciences (IUCE, Universidad de Salamanca).

The aim of this project is:

To study de evolution of educational equity levels in secondary education and to promote the main educational protective factors.

This aim will be achieved in three phases, presented in chronological order:

1. **Study of the evolution of educational equity in secondary education** from PISA data (2000-2018) under two approaches:
 - a. Equity as equal achievement. Evolution of achievement variability in a country or region.
 - b. Equity as equal opportunities. Progress of the relationship between a measure of family socioeconomic level (SES) and achievement, both at student and school levels; and evolution of school segregation, defined as the variability of SES at school level.
2. **Identification of educational factors that promote educational equity**, from the analysis of PISA 2018 and 2022 waves.
3. **Design, implementation and assessment of training programmes on educational equity** aimed at school heads, guidance counsellors and key actors in secondary education.

Phase one: evolution of educational equity

Within phase one of the Project, this report presents indicators for educational equity and school segregation obtained in Italy. In order to facilitate a comparative analysis, the results of each indicator will be accompanied by the average of European countries (EU members) and the average of the OECD countries to act as a baseline.

As a member of the Project in Italy, once you receive the report you will be asked to:

Analyse the evolution of educational equity in your country and consider the possible influence of changes in socioeconomic conditions and socio-educational policies on this evolution.

Interpretation of equity indicators

An education system should strive not just to reach high competence or achievement levels, but also acceptable and generalized achievement levels in most students and schools (equal achievement) and to ensure the same access to education (equal opportunities):

Indicators for equity as equal achievement

INDICATOR	LEVEL	UNIT	FORMULA	EXPLANATION
Variation Coefficient (CV)	Student	Percentage (%)	$CV (\%) = \frac{S_x}{ \bar{x} } * 100$	<p>CV indicates how disperse or heterogeneous the values of a variable are (in this case the variable is student achievement). A CV=0% indicates that all students or schools have obtained exactly the same achievement level. The indicator at student level refers to the differences in achievement among the students of a country, and the indicator at school level refers to the differences among the schools' average scores.</p> <p>In order to interpret this indicator, you can use the following reference points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CV=20% → Average achievement differences • CV<20% → Achievement differences below average • CV>20% → Achievement differences above average <p>In an education system, differences in student achievement (CV at student level) are to be expected, but a high CV at school level would indicate that there are schools with vastly different average scores, which would violate the principle of equity as equal achievement.</p>
	School			
ICC of achievement	School	Percentage (%)	$Rend_{ij} = \gamma_{00} + u_{0j} + e_{ij}$ $Ineq_{ir} = \frac{\sigma_j^2}{\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2}$ <p>*Rend= achievement Ineq_{ir} = ICC_{achievement} Subindex <i>i</i> is for student Subindex <i>j</i> is for school</p>	<p>ICC_{achievement} indicates the percentage of the total variance of the achievement of a country's students ($\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2$) that can be explained by the grouping of students in schools (σ_j^2 or between school variability), considering σ_i^2 as the variability of students within a school (within school variability).</p> <p>In order to interpret this indicator, you can use the following reference points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICC<20% → The average achievement of schools is very similar, there is a low achievement inequality due to the grouping of students in schools • ICC>60% → The average achievement of schools is very different, the grouping of students in schools is highly unequal <p>A country with similar schools according to its achievement levels (low ICC) is equitable: this indicates that there is no student segregation based on achievement. On the contrary, high levels of ICC indicate that students are highly segregated based on their achievement, and this promotes inequality.</p>

Indicators for equity as equal opportunities

INDICATOR	LEVEL	UNIT	FORMULA	EXPLANATION
Pearson's correlation (R_{xy})	Student	Score ranging from (-1 , 1)	$R_{xy} = \frac{S_{xy}}{S_x * S_y}$ <p>* Y= Achievement X= Socioeconomic level</p>	<p>This correlation indicates the type and intensity of the relationship between two variables: achievement and socioeconomic status (SES). A value of $R_{xy}=0$ indicates that achievement and SES are independent, therefore the country is equitable.</p> <p>R_{xy} at student level indicates the relationship between the two variables in all the students from a country. R_{xy} at school level indicates the relationship between all the schools' average achievement and average SES.</p> <p>At student level, the indicator can be interpreted as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $R_{xy} < 0.30 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a small relationship $R_{xy} > 0.45 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a large relationship <p>At school level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $R_{xy} < 0.40 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a small relationship $R_{xy} > 0.80 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a large relationship <p>There is a clear and direct R_{xy} between these two variables at an international level (high-SES students have higher achievements and vice versa), which is a relevant source of inequity: favourable socioeconomic conditions facilitate a greater academic success, thus limiting the equitable access to education and hindering the social promotion that an education system should promote.</p>
	School			
ICC of SES	School	Percentage (%)	$NSE_{ij} = \gamma_{00} + u_{0j} + e_{ij}$ $Segr. = \frac{\sigma_j^2}{\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2}$ <p>*NSE=SES Segregation. = ICC_{SES} Subindex i is for student Subindex j is for school</p>	<p>ICC_{NSE} indicates the percentage of the total variance of the SES of a country's students ($\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2$) that can be explained by the grouping of students in schools (σ_j^2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $ICC < 20\% \rightarrow$ The average achievement of schools is very similar, there is a low achievement inequality due to the grouping of students in schools $ICC > 45\% \rightarrow$ The average achievement of schools is very different, the grouping of students in schools is highly inequal <p>A country where schools have similar average SES (low ICC) is equitable: there is no segregation of students based on their SES. A high ICC indicates inequity due to socioeconomic segregation.</p>
School inequity (SI)	School and student	Percentage (%)	$inequ. = \frac{\sigma_{jnull}^2 - \sigma_{jfinal}^2}{\sigma_{jnull}^2}$ <p>* Inequ. = IE Subindex j is for school</p>	<p>School Inequity (SI) indicates the percentage of the total variability of achievement at school level which can be explained by SES, that is, the impact of SES in a country's achievement. In a country with a high SI, low-SES students have many difficulties in order to access education and to benefit from social promotion through education. This indicator can be interpreted as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $SI < 25\% \rightarrow$ Low SES does not hinder an equitable access to education $SI > 55\% \rightarrow$ Low SES hinders an equitable access to education <p>This is the main indicator of equity as equal opportunities in a country, since it encompasses the partial information shown by both R_{xy} scores mentioned above.</p>

Evolution of equity indicators in the country

Below you will find the results obtained in Italy, both in terms of the country's evolution as well as a comparison of said evolution against the average of European countries and OECD members.

Evolution of equity as equal achievement

Table 1 provides data of the indicators that explore the variability of achievement in the education system, both at student and school level.

Table 1. Evolution of equity as equal achievement indicators

		2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018
CV_{student}	Italy	18.24%	19.43%	19.56%	18.49%	18.24%	17.92%	18.36%
	EU	19,14%	18,04%	18,19%	18,15%	17,89%	18,37%	18,38%
	OECD	18,56%	18,22%	18,23%	17,84%	17,91%	18,10%	18,29%
CV_{school}	Italy	20.01%	23.15%	19.44%	18.25%	17.14%	14.65%	16.57%
	EU	15,49%	13,51%	13,75%	13,51%	13,78%	13,09%	13,66%
	OECD	14,50%	13,36%	13,64%	13,06%	13,47%	12,50%	13,15%
ICC_{achievement}	Italy	56.35%	60.83%	60.81%	57.99%	60.39%	49.15%	54.40%
	EU	47,54%	42,65%	46,01%	45,59%	46,54%	41,50%	42,57%
	OECD	44,42%	39,74%	42,57%	42,16%	42,91%	38,11%	39,09%

Graph 1 shows that the variation coefficient for students in Italy has maintained a rather stable evolution, keeping in line with EU and OECD levels.

Graph 1. Evolution of the variation coefficient (CV) at student level

Graph 2 shows a similar picture for the variation coefficient at school level for EU and OECD averages. Italy's score in the indicator goes up from 2000 to 2003, and then it shows a steady decline until 2015, with a slight increase in 2018. Although Italy is always above OECD and EU levels, it seems to be getting closer to them in the past few years.

Graph 2. Evolution of the variation coefficient (CV) at school level

Graph 3 show a fairly steady evolution of inequity measured as unequal distribution of achievement at school level, with a slight decrease in the past two PISA editions.

Graph 3. Evolution of ICC achievement (school inequity due to unequal achievement distribution)

Evolution of equity as equal opportunities

Table 2 provides data on all indicators related to equal opportunities in education, assessed mainly through the relationship between SES and achievement at student and school levels (School Inequity).

Table 2. Evolution of equity as equal opportunities indicators

		2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018
Rxy_{student}	Italy	0.30	0.41	0.32	0.35	0.33	0.34	0.33
	EU	0,39	0,44	0,40	0,40	0,41	0,39	0,39
	OECD	0,39	0,43	0,39	0,40	0,39	0,37	0,38
Rxy_{school}	Italy	0.39	0.67	0.57	0.59	0.70	0.73	0.58
	EU	0,64	0,70	0,66	0,66	0,69	0,68	0,67
	OECD	0,64	0,71	0,66	0,66	0,67	0,65	0,65
ICC_{SES}	Italy	32.97%	32.83%	29.50%	29.50%	29.73%	29.18%	28.49%
	EU	31,27%	29,40%	31,28%	30,95%	31,73%	29,70%	30,75%
	OECD	31,77%	28,70%	29,54%	29,58%	30,09%	28,71%	29,91%
School Inequity	Italy	31.13%	43.14%	40.11%	39.10%	41.32%	48.16%	44.15%
	EU	45,51%	46,27%	43,99%	47,80%	47,53%	52,29%	53,53%
	OECD	38,58%	46,96%	42,60%	43,62%	44,23%	49,15%	50,32%

Figure 4 shows a relative stability in the correlation between performance and SES at student level at all three levels (OECD, EU and Italy) especially from 2006 onwards.

Graph 4. Evolution of achievement-SES correlation at student level

Graph 5 shows that the levels of the correlation between achievement and SES at school level in the OECD and EU behave similarly to the previous graph. However, the evolution of Italy is somewhat more variable, levels close to OECD and EU averages from 2012 onwards.

Graph 5. Evolution of achievement-SES correlation at school level

Graph 6 shows the evolution of the degree of segregation of students in schools according to their SES. In the case of Italy, the evolution is highly stable, with levels below EU average and nearly identical to OECD averages.

Graph 6. Evolution of ICC SES (inequity due to SES distribution)

Graph 7 shows an evolution with an upward tendency for School Inequity in the case of Italy, with the indicator going up from 30% to around 45% in the past two decades. The same tendency, albeit with slightly higher scores, can be observed in the EU and OECD.

Graph 7. Evolution of School Inequity (difficulty for social promotion through education)

Global score of the indicators

Table 3 provides data on global scores (average of the scores obtained 2000-2018) for each indicator, compared to EU and OECD averages.

Table 3. Evolution of equity indicators

		Italy	EU	OECD
Equity as equal achievement	CV_{student}	18.61%	18,29%	18,15%
	CV_{school}	18.46%	13,78%	13,36%
	ICC_{achievement}	57.13%	44,59%	41,24%
Equity as equal opportunities	Rxy_{student}	0.34	0,40	0,39
	Rxy_{school}	0.60	0,67	0,66
	ICC_{SES}	30.31%	30,75%	29,72%
	School Inequity	41.01%	47,13%	45,21%

This information is also presented in graph form (graph 8). Italy's scores, which are above average in two of the three indicators related to equity as equal achievement, indicate that school are indeed somewhat segregated according to student achievement. However, the indicators related to equity as equal opportunities seem to indicate that Italy's education system is more equitable in that regard than EU and OECD countries on average.

Graph 8. Global equity scores